

Generation of enteroids from fresh porcine jejunum

Note: for the reagents refer to “List of reagents for enteroid protocols” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13847508)

- 1) Collect a section of 5-10 cm of jejunum from pigs no older than 5 months
- 2) Open up the jejunum longitudinally and wash in ice-cold PBSL for 4 times
- 3) Remove villi by gentle scrapping with a coverslip
- 4) Wash off the villi with ice-cold PBSL
- 5) Cut the intestine into pieces of around 2-3 mm³ and transfer them to a 50 mL tube
- 6) Wash the pieces with ice-cold PBSL by vigorous shaking
- 7) Repeat step 6) until the supernatant is almost clear
Note: At this step, pieces can be frozen (see steps 8-10) or processed for the isolation of crypts (continue with steps 8-25)
- 8) Remove supernatant and transfer pieces in cryovials containing 1 mL of Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) with 10% DMSO
- 9) Freeze cryovials slowly in an appropriate cell freezing container and place at -80°C for 24h
- 10) Transfer cryovials in liquid nitrogen for long-term storage
- 11) Transfer the jejunum pieces in 20 mL of Dissociation Buffer and incubate for 20' on ice on a rocking platform
- 12) After the incubation remove the dissociation buffer
- 13) Add 15 mL PBSL+2%FBS
- 14) Shake the tube vigorously
- 15) Let the pieces fall by gravity and collect the first washing fraction (fraction 1)
- 16) Repeat step 13-15 for 5-6 times and collect fractions (fraction 2-6)
- 17) Pass each fraction through a 100 µm cell strainer into a 50 mL tube to remove villi
- 18) Take about 50 µL of each fraction and check at the microscope the amount of crypts
- 19) Select the fractions containing the larger amount of crypts and the lower amount of debris and villi
- 20) Under the microscope, estimate the number of crypts in a 50 µL drop of the selected fraction and calculate the total number for each fraction
- 21) Spin the selected fraction at 400 rcf for 5' at 4°C
- 22) Resuspend the crypt fraction in the appropriate volume of 70% Geltrex™ in DMEM/F12. Approx 30-50 crypts should be diluted in 28 µL Geltrex™ and 12 µL DMEM/F12 per well (use a 24 well tissue culture plate). Keep tube on ice
- 23) Dispense a drop of 40 µL for each well and incubate the plate for 10' at 37°C.
- 24) Add 500 µL complete medium (CM)
- 25) Change medium after 2-3 days.